

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

FLAGSHIP PROJECT CIRIL

SPOKE N 3 – CULTURAL-INDUSTRY REGENERATION IMMERSIVE LAB

DELIVERABLE D 3.2: Technological mock-up for personalised itineraries

REPORTING PERIOD	
Period covered:	from (May 2024) to (September 2024)
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Milestone 8.1 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito
RM8 Responsible	Prof. Paolo Esposito

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to "Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
NODES' Research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES' Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES' Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke's ecosystem. It refers to "Spoke" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione"
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke's ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke' leadership and management. It refers to "soggetti affiliati" in the MUR's Call of proposal for "Ecosistemi di Innovazione".
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be the responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES' Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be the responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

List of Deliverables

#	Name	Type		Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
D3.1	Context related analysis of lesser known cultural areas	R	PU	12	30/03/2024			03/04/2024
D3.2	Technological mock-up for personalised itineraries	R	PU	18	30/09/2024			03/10/2024
D3.3	Methodology and training contents based on immersive technologies approach	R	PU	24				
D3.4	SHERIL Pilot	DEM	PU	32				

List of Milestone

#	Name	Type	Due month	Due date	Short description	New Due Date (if delay)	Delivery Date (actual)
M1	Analysis of the state of art and Point of Interests (POI)	R	10	04/02/2024	.		04/04/2024
M2	Main user domain and user content defined		14	30/05/2024			04/06/2024

A) EXPLANATION OF THE WORK CARRIED OUT AND OVERVIEW OF THE PROGRESS

1. Introduction

1.1 Objective of the Deliverable

Deliverable D2 entitled " Technological mock-up for personalised itineraries " is started in April 2024, at the achievement of the D1 named " Context related analysis of lesser known cultural areas ". This deliverable is a crucial component of our project, aimed at demonstrating the functionality and user experience of our personalized itinerary solution.

During this period are achieved completely the Milestone M2 titled "Main user domain and user content defined". After analysing how visitor attendance in lesser-known cultural areas can be increased through the adoption of ICT, a crucial research theme that emerged is the public value creation generated by the use of innovative technologies in cultural heritage.

1.2 Context

The Research Team is composed by Professor Gerardo Canfora, Rector of University del Sannio, Gaetano Natullo, Director of Department of Law, Economics, Management and Quantitative Methods (DEMM), Paolo Esposito, Angelo Riviezzo, Biagio Simonetti and Pasquale Vito. Other two Member of the Research Team are: Piera Zerillo, Research Fellow, and Massimiliano Tufo, Ph.D. Student.

In July 2024, Vitiana L'Abate, a new researcher, was recruited with a fellowship financed by the NODES project's financial resources and joined the Research Team.

2. Methodology

The activities implemented are manifold and consist of:

- Literature review in the frame of the project;
- Bibliographic collection;
- Multiple case study methodology.

3. Results

The empirical observation and the sources are examined in the light of common and differential elements: one was in the phase before the management experiment and was not publicly accessible. One of its main focuses is the development of new technologies and applications in the ICT domain discloses new opportunities to add value to, and promote the natural, historical, socio-cultural, creative, and economic heritage, with positive consequences on the tourism industry. On one hand, technology can be

leveraged to improve the cultural fruition of the territory (i.e., AR or VR applied to enrich a museum or an exhibition or an archaeological site visitor's experience) to the advantage of tourists as well as local inhabitants. On the other hand, technology can be used to integrate, first, and then effectively promote an overarching touristic proposal, especially by expressing an identity which is terroir-specific (i.e., based on the local excellences) and highlighting its inherent sustainability.

Therefore, it can be inferred, in the perspective of the literature study and case study observation, that the integration of innovation and tradition in cultural organisations is developed by:

- new divisive technologies from mobile devices to new immersive environments VR, AR, XR;
- 3D source-based reconstructions of heritage in specific historical periods;
- spherical photogrammetry and VR environments through graphics engines for real-time 3D application;
- adoption of ICT and the implementation of new technological architectures;
- Immersive and Virtual Reality systems for research, education and business development services.

4. Conclusion

The activities are devoted to foster the dissemination of knowledge by contextualising information in cultural sites. The conducted Literature Review indicate that tourist engagement and use of technology play a key role in personalised itineraries, suggesting the importance of understanding cultural factors to optimise the tourist experience and improve engagement with immersive technologies in the tourism industry. In this research, we interpret tourist engagement as the emotional, psychological and behavioural relationship with a tourist destination, a place or attraction that can be a museum or a tourist site (Chathoth et al., 2014). Interestingly, tourists' involvement may vary according to different variables: for example, their involvement may differ according to whether they are tourists visiting a place for the first time or according to their gender (Rasoolimanesh et al., 2021), or even according to the use of technology during all phases of their trip (Loureiro & Sarmiento, 2019), which seems to greatly enhance the overall experience (Kearsley & Shneiderman, 1998).

Various studies have delved into the effects and applications of virtual reality (VR) in museum settings, aiming to elevate visitor experiences and interactions (Lee et al., 2020; Hollebeek et al., 2020; Flaviàn et al., 2019; Hammady et al., 2021; Pengnate et al., 2021). This form of cultural site experience is on the rise, driven by the captivating interest it incites in visitors as they embark on immersive and emotionally stimulating journeys facilitated by intricate designs and digital tools. Regretfully, there are currently no research projects that connect the employment of new technology in museums to a rise in the value that is created for both the region and its visitors. The only recent study that makes use of augmented reality (AR) was done by Izzo et al. (2023). The findings of this study demonstrate how new technologies have the potential to significantly contribute to the

creation of value for visitors, the museum, and society at large. The use of technology in cultural site settings has increased significantly during the past ten years. In this way, a significant portion of legacy is appreciated outside the home due to cutting-edge multimedia products.

The research develops by analysing the theoretical framework on public value because it is crucial comprehend how Innovation Communication Technologies (ICTs) can create public value in cultural heritage. This perspective has two significant implications, both for research and for private and public tourism management. First, it provides insights into the factors that contribute to tourist engagement and the future use of technology in an archaeological cultural site. The results of this study also have implications for management and tourism professionals who seek to enhance the visitor experience through immersive technology offerings. Moreover, future investigation could focus not only on public value creation but also public value destruction.

5. Contribution of the Deliverable to NODES Objectives

The completion of Deliverable D2 marks a significant milestone in our project development. The technological mock-up for personalized itineraries not only demonstrates our envisioned solution but also incorporates valuable user feedback that will inform the next stages of development.

Last but not least, the theoretical framework of the analysis, concerning public value creation and public value destruction, is part of a paper presented in a Scientific Conference called "SIDREA 2024 Conference", which was particularly appreciated and received several feedbacks from academics and practitioners during the conference.

In September, two new publications were published in EuroMed Academy of Business Conference Book of Proceedings (Book Series). This Book of Proceedings have been approved for inclusion in the Conference Proceedings Citation Index — of Clarivate Analytics an integrated index within Web of Science. This distinction is given only to the most significant papers, in terms of academic excellence, conferences-conventions worldwide. Additionally, the two papers published in the EMAB 2024 Conference, have been selected together with a small number of papers (<20%) for inclusion in, each as chapters, in a book of the Scopus-indexed Book Series "Palgrave Studies in Cross-Disciplinary Business Research, In Association with EuroMed Academy of Business", published by Palgrave Macmillan (Springer).

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